

Psychosocial Interventions in Adolescents with Emotional Dysregulation

Aldo Diavoletto ✉, Franca Bottiglieri, Marianna Sessa, Antonietta Franco, Manuela Di Nome, Daniela Caserta

Childhood and Adolescent Neuropsychiatry Operating Unit (UONPIA) Salerno, ASL Salerno, Italy

Abstract

Adolescents with emotional dysregulation (ED) and related clinical pictures represent a group of patients characterized by extreme fragility in terms of development and in terms of scholastic and social adaptation. Children and adolescents with ADHD, mood disorders and borderline personality disorder share ED, which involves cognitive, adaptive and social difficulties. After diagnosis, non-pharmacological interventions in adolescence include psychotherapy, group Social Skill Training, parent training for parents, both single-family and group. The authors present an experience of taking charge of adolescents in a small group with group Social Skill Training combined with multi-family parent training.

Introduction

Adolescents with emotional dysregulation (ED) and related clinical pictures represent a group of patients characterized by extreme fragility in terms of development and in terms of scholastic and social adaptation. Both psychopathological drifts, as well as socio-professional failure, and antisocial drifts are possible. Often, management by families is very difficult, especially if there are other risk factors and parental availability alone is not sufficient.

Children and adolescents with ADHD, Oppositional Defiant Disorder, mood disorders and Borderline Personality Disorder share difficulties in emotional regulation, which are associated with significant global cognitive, adaptive and psychosocial dysfunctions.

The term Emotional Dysregulation (ED) represents a transdiagnostic construct consisting of the inability to regulate the intensity and quality of emotions and to generate an appropriate response to manage excitability, mood instability and hyperreactivity [1]. It depends on constitutional factors, traumatic events and characteristics of early relational experiences.

dysregulation is therefore a condition that runs through many symptomatic pictures of developmental psychopathology and manifests itself as a maladaptive

processing of internal or external stimuli when the emotional regulation systems are compromised. Most of the time the impairment is disabling in all life contexts; reactions appear excessive, inadequate compared to the most basic rules of social life: at school or in other social or recreational contexts with peers and adults, reactions of extreme excitability, mood instability, irritability, hypersensitivity up to excesses in behavior and aggressiveness are recorded.

In young children, dysregulation mainly concerns behavior and sometimes the somatic aspect. As regards relational correlates, according to several authors [2], from 2 and a half to 5 years of age approximately, the symptoms seem to be linked to maternal depression and poor maternal educational skills. Other research correlates emotional dysregulation towards the age of 10 with difficulties in *social skills*, specifically the ability to *make decisions*. *making* [3].

dysregulation in children is also typically related to ADHD as highlighted by several researches [4].

Although current evidence-based treatments for ADHD can improve academic and behavioral functioning, they appear to have little impact on social functioning or risky behaviors [5]. Preliminary evidence indicates that emotional dysregulation (ED) is associated with

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adolescents, emotional dysregulation, social skill training, parent training.

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impairments across the developmental spectrum, such as social impairment and risky behaviors, and that it is closely related to functional *outcomes*. It is therefore obvious that ED in ADHD children needs to be better addressed in interventions targeting social impairment and risky behaviors; however, the extent to which ED is associated with the above-mentioned impairments and behaviors should be investigated, and the extent to which ED is modifiable should be investigated.

In Hirsch [6] there is the hypothesis that ED is a distinct symptom of adult ADHD. The comprehensive assessment of ED contributes to a deeper understanding of the disorders related to adult ADHD and can be used for further differentiation of subgroups within these patients.

Furthermore, ED may have a direct role on dysfunctional social behavior, affects developmental outcomes in adulthood [7] and in turn may affect the next generation. Cleminshaw [8] also correlates ED to scholastic and adaptive difficulties in ADHD.

Emotional regulation depends on early relationships, as a co-regulation in tune with the *caregiver*. In fact, from the first years of life, the child actively engages in achieving internal stability, a sort of homeostasis, which depends on the regulatory functions of the brainstem. These functions are responsible for keeping sleep-wake rhythms, breathing, hydration and other basic vital functions under control [9]. During this phase, the *caregiver* plays an essential role in facilitating these processes and in helping the child to develop an increasingly sophisticated capacity for regulating his internal states. Subsequently, with the progressive development of brain structures, increasingly more articulated and complex self-regulation mechanisms develop [9].

Some research [10] recalls the transgenerational importance of emotional regulation, that is, the characteristics of the emotional regulation of mothers and fathers influence that of their children.

In adolescence, poor regulation, with predictable clinical correlates, may also depend on stressful and maladaptive events in childhood: in a sample of 3915 adolescents, the role of child abuse and impulsivity in non-suicidal self-harm behaviors was highlighted [11]. Unlike what happens during childhood, in adolescence we observe an expansion of the social sphere of individuals. This period is characterized by an immaturity of the frontal lobe, which is responsible for evaluation and inhibition, unlike the limbic system which instead governs emotional processing. Consequently, in front of intense emotional stimuli, vigorous impulses and a *sensation are manifested seeking* that cannot be easily controlled. This leads adolescents to have greater difficulty managing emotions than adults and children [12].

Adolescence therefore represents a particularly critical period for emotional regulation skills and many authors believe that they are characterized by non-linear transitions [13-14]. In this regard, a very interesting model is the *maladaptive shift model*, which maintains that during adolescence a dysfunctional change (*maladaptive*) occurs (*shift*) in emotional regulation which could be explained by biological and psychological changes [13]. In particular, the neuro-endocrinological changes that accompany puberty and that occur, among other things, in conjunction with the new and challenging developmental tasks that adolescents have to face on their path towards autonomy [14] would be crucial.

Numerous evidences suggest, in fact, that adolescents experience negative emotions with greater frequency and intensity than both children and adults [13], in the absence of sufficiently effective cognitive control strategies, and this could lead to a decrease in the use of adaptive regulation strategies and an increase in maladaptive ones [15]. In fact, intensity is also influenced by the state of mind at a specific moment, so that some emotional responses can sometimes seem exaggerated, while sometimes sensitivity can be reduced to external stimuli.

According to a study by Silvers and colleagues [16], emotion management processes are influenced by various factors, including age, situational circumstances and individual differences. The results indicate that age-related differences in the ability to regulate emotions are more evident in response to social than to non-social stimuli, and that individuals with high rejection sensitivity tend to have more difficulties in managing their emotional responses to adverse situations, especially at a young age. These data suggest that learning to regulate one's emotions is a challenge and an evolutionary process, which most people successfully face during adolescence. However, individuals with high rejection sensitivity may develop low self-esteem and encounter difficulties in social interactions during middle and late adolescence [16]. Furthermore, as outlined by Gross [17], several processes come into play in the modification of an emotional state before the overall "dysregulation" that may eventually be observed. These processes include the individual's ability to select, attend to, and evaluate emotionally arousing stimuli that lead to the experience of an emotional state both physiologically and behaviorally. Subsequently, modulation efforts occur both unconsciously and consciously in response to that emotional state to promote an adaptive emotional response.

The difficulties in treating ED depend on the fact that it is structured over time as a defense and avoidance strategy such as dissociation, numbness or detachment; these strategies bring with them non-

negligible secondary advantages and can persist even after the improvement of the main symptoms.

Several authors also highlight the centrality of ED in the development of Borderline Personality Disorder as well as in self-harming behaviors and suicide attempts [18; 19; 20].

In order to work in an articulated way on psychic suffering in developmental age in the various disorders it is necessary to connect it to ED. For this purpose, the concept of "window of tolerance" introduced by Daniel Siegel in 2012 [21] seems to us to be particularly useful clinically. The "window of tolerance" is nothing other than a sort of physiological "fluctuation" of the state of *arousal* downwards and upwards, with respect to activating or containing situations. The young patient with ED, in fact, is unable to find strategies to re-enter the window of tolerance, when one finds oneself outside it, both in terms of hyper or hypo *arousal* [21]. Social skills or SS correspond to the tools with which individuals communicate, interact, learn, ask for help, satisfy needs, develop relationships, and adapt autonomously to society [22]. The concept of SS is linked to intelligence, quality of life, and social and work adaptation. The creation of good interpersonal and/or friendly relationships is considered the crucial mediator between SS and good outcomes in a social sense and in terms of individual gratification [23].

Children with ED often have more social and emotional problems than their peers: they may have difficulty decoding social cues, for example, they may interrupt or have difficulty waiting their turn; they may have problems learning social skills, such as starting or maintaining a conversation and *problem-solving*; they may have difficulty controlling their behavior and emotions. They may sometimes be very impulsive or aggressive, they may have difficulty cooperating or studying or playing with peers. It is then possible that peers find their behavior inappropriate or irritating. In fact, adolescents with ADHD may be rejected by their peers because they are considered intrusive and annoying [24]. According to some studies, between 50% and 80% of children with ADHD are unaccepted by the group, which represents a relevant component of the social deficit in ADHD and is not easy to amend [25 – 26] as well as being a critical indicator for subsequent maladjustment and unfavorable *outcomes* [27].

The deficit in the perception of social rules, among other things, weakens the understanding of this difficulty by the subject with ED and/or ADHD, which further worsens adaptive functions with peers.

Referring to Gresham's model [28] according to which there are two levels of deficit in SS, a deficit in the acquisition of social competence and a deficit in social performance, it is believed that in ADHD social skills would be present, but are not applied in a way that is consistent with the developmental level [29].

According to McQuade and Hoza [30 – 31], the social deficit related to performance could depend on ED with poor emotional literacy, deficit in the processing of inadequate social information, with relative overestimation of one's social competence. Children with ED have greater difficulty in integrating and organizing social signals coherently [32].

In ED, anger, frustration, hostility prevail. All these characteristics cause impulsivity to result in a loss of relevant social information and a tendency to respond in an irrelevant way to relational situations.

Around the 1990s, *social skills training* (SST) was developed which have shown good results in some areas but not in all, for example they are not always effective with respect to the judgment of peers towards the patient [33 - 34]. Furthermore, recent literature underlines the importance of giving greater body and structure to studies to verify the effectiveness of the results.

Prosocial behaviors, in understanding the emotional states of peers, in developing functional solutions to social problems or in modifying his erroneous beliefs [33]. Group intervention obviously provides more opportunities to structure interventions of reflection on emotions and to experiment prosocial behaviors.

In a 2010 study [35] there were 120 children with ADHD. SST led to greater improvements in assertiveness skills perceived by both parents and the child in children but did not influence other domains of social competence. Children with comorbid oppositional defiant disorder (ODD) did not benefit greatly from the intervention.

In a 2019 review by Storebo [36], social skills interventions were detailed into the following categories: 1) social skills training, 2) cognitive behavioral therapy, 3) multimodal behavioral/psychosocial therapy, 4) child life and attention skills treatment, 5) life skills training, 6) the "Challenge Horizon Program," 7) verbal self-instruction, 8) metacognitive training, 9) behavioral therapy, 10) behavioral and social skills treatment, and 11) psychosocial treatment.

The duration of the interventions ranged from five weeks to two years. Most studies compared child social skills training or parent training combined with medication versus medication alone. The certainty of the evidence of effectiveness was not rated as satisfactory.

Recent models [37] suggest that any ineffectiveness of social skills training for children with ADHD may be due to misspecification of goals, conceptualizations that suggest that social problems in ADHD primarily reflect inconsistent performance rather than a lack of social knowledge/skills, which has implications for refinement of interventions themselves.

Choi [38] also emphasizes the importance of emotional education in addition to SST.

In school contexts [39] working with children with *social skills deficits*, the results indicate that the SSGT is widely applicable and socially valid, and a wider implementation of the SSGT in school settings seems significant and desirable.

According to Sibley [40], to improve the quality of care, evidence-based practices should be implemented (e.g., parent involvement, use of measurement-based parameters, training in organizational skills, use of operant reinforcement).

Parent Training (PT) is a diversified set of interventions that aim to support the parental couple in managing problematic aspects of their children, which can manifest themselves both in the behavioral and emotional-relational fields [41]. Obviously, parent training is structured on the basis of a vast literature, considering how the evolutionary trajectory of a child is strictly related to the context, to the relationship with parents and family. ED on the one hand often appears in families with elements of dysfunctionality, on the other it complicates the management of intra-family relationships and the implementation of adequate educational practices, so that parenting alone is not sufficient, and some families are particularly affected by the child's disorder. Parents can become hyper-controlling, punitive, tend to express high emotionality, increasing the child's evolutionary risk and fueling a vicious circle tending towards opposition, challenge and the structuring of a negative identity of the child.

Related to this concept is the concept of family burden or "*burden*" [42], dependent on the difficulties related to the management of the child's pathology. A typical construct in the management of chronic mental pathology, it is distinguished into objective or subjective burden, if linked to emotional factors or consisting of concrete limitations (work, financial).

Parent training can be considered an integral part of therapeutic interventions with an adolescent and serves to provide parents with information on the clinical picture and on the causes and functional effects of the symptoms, and above all concrete pedagogical indications.

The aim of parent training is therefore to improve relationships, reduce problem behaviors, promote emerging skills, improve self-esteem and the child's socio-scholastic skills.

What needs to be encouraged is the development of an educational style that is as comprehensible and homogeneous as possible, coherent and constant on the basis of an affective presupposition. It is always better for parent training to take place in a group, because meeting other parents involved in similar experiences produces a feeling of lightening the load,

of sharing stories and the fact of learning together with others proves very profitable [43]. In parent training, basic elements can be acquired in order to structure daily life, but sometimes bonds are also created that can continue outside the context of care.

As regards the educational attitude, parents are trained to work on emotions but also to apply techniques specific to behavioural therapy such as the "*Token-Economy*" [44] in the formulation of rules, and the "*time-out*" [45].

Since the reactions of the subject with ED to punishments and rewards are different from those of his peers and, more precisely, educational aids have a more impactful effect, it is necessary to focus on rewards and support for functional behaviors. It is appropriate to mention some contents of the training: Promote release and the appropriate search for independence: parents must allow the adolescent experiences in small doses, and encourage only when the boy shows he is responsible. Maintain adequate supervision: it is necessary for parents to be "mentally" present, to control the child longer and more closely, in relation to the boy's symptoms, dosing concessions and control.

New families see vague models, blurred values, fathers often withdrawn or absent, or broken families, or extended or reconstituted. These new family models like "traditional" families require a lot of support work. First of all, families must be taught to re-establish roles or recover them. The main weak point of parents today is the weakening of roles and the fear of making mistakes, which generates indiscriminate laxity or educational paralysis: fixed rules must be given to deal with problematic situations (homework, curfew, compulsive use of video games ...). It is necessary to keep in mind what is negotiable from what is not: respect for social norms and those established by law and fundamental values cannot be the object of negotiation; Actual violence (aggression to things or people in cases of serious behavioral disorders) must not be tolerated, nor can it be negotiated. It is necessary to place insurmountable constraints on it, even at the cost of asking for external help (judicial authority).

You can and must negotiate with the adolescent regarding other issues Give parents directives to strengthen their role, use rewards before punishing and only punish when necessary: these are all behaviors aimed at strengthening authority; it is essential that they remember to never make promises or threats that they are not sure they can keep; work on communication skills and the ability to express opinions and requests in an appropriate manner; work on Expressed Emotionality Focus on the strengths of the child and the family unit by encouraging positive

and rewarding experiences both for individual members and for the entire unit

There are different models, all of which include: an initial phase in which parents are informed about the clinical picture, what has been done, what can still be done, and the problem and current dysfunctions are discussed; a phase in which strategies are transmitted to achieve the set objectives, with behavioral suggestions but also emotional and relational reading of experiences and contexts

The average duration of a PT consists of at least 10 sessions in a small group.

As per a large literature, PT usually produces positive effects both on the management of the child and on the psychological well-being of the family, even after a long time [46; 47].

The results appear less favorable when there are additional problems, such as socio-economic disadvantage, psychiatric pathology of a parent, conflictual marital dynamics, presence of *addiction* in the family history, parental methods tending towards rigidity and/or coercion.

Purpose of the Work: to report an experience of psychosocial intervention in a small group of adolescents with Emotional Dysregulation .

Materials and Methods

We thought we should take charge of a small group of troubled adolescents.

6 patients, age 15 years and 6 months-18 years.

- Male- mild MRI – ADHD - PDO
- Male -FIL ADHD
- Male -FIL, ADHD
- Male -DPB with psychotic overtones
- Male -BPD with psychotic overtones
- Female-BPD

The clinical picture presented to us by the families and the anamnesis was related to socio-scholastic failure and deficient or borderline cognitive functioning, relational inadequacy with inappropriate and sometimes bizarre behaviors, personality traits close to psychotic-type functioning. The common transdiagnostic trait was the serious difficulty in emotional regulation. The ability to deal with others in a flexible way, to regulate the right emotional distance from the interlocutor, to get involved in a participatory, playful or *problem-solving activity appeared to be compromised in all of them. solving* , difficulty understanding and expressing one's emotions and experiences.

All of them benefited from a structured evaluation with the following instruments: WISC-IV or WAIS-IV, Vineland , CBCL, Conners , ERI-RAOS.

The intervention lasted 18 months, with fortnightly meetings.

Psychosocial characteristics of the sample, based on the structured diagnostic material and the type of needs expressed:

- Cognitive dysfunction with IQ at or below the normal range
- Behavioral and educational dysfunction
- School and social maladjustment , poor friendship network
- Incompetent families, in one case a mother with cognitive limitations.
- High “ *burden* ” and sense of dissatisfaction with the treatment paths experienced
- transdiagnostic element : difficulty regulating emotions

Measurable improvements: adaptive functions were assessed with the Vineland 2 scale [48], with particular reference to the socialization subscale , and clinical severity with the CGI scale, [49 – 50] before and after the intervention; parenting difficulties were assessed with the Parenting Stress Index (PSI) scale [51].

Results and Discussion

The following table highlights the results before and after the intervention with the help of the VABS socialization subscale , and the CGI-C and CGIS scales as well as the PSI scale.

- Patient 1 CGI-S moderate severity CGI-C minimal improvement
- Paz 2 CGI-S mild severity CGI-C minimal improvement
- Paz 3 CGI-S moderate severity CGI-C minimal improvement
- Paz 4 CGI-S moderate severity CGI-C -no improvement
- Paz 5 CGI-S moderate severity CGI-C no improvement
- Paz 6 CGI-S moderate severity CGI-C minimal improvement

Figure 1: Pre and post CGI-S and CGI-C

Table 1: Pre and Post Vineland

	Pre	Post
1	low mod	low mod
2	low mod	low
3	low mod	low
4	low	low mod
5	low mod	low mod
6	low	low

Figure 2: Pre and Post Vineland

Table 2: Parent Stress Index

	Pre	Post
1	59/112	61/112
2	55/112	59/112
3	51/112	55/112
4	55/112	59/112
5	51/112	55/112
6	46/112	11/112

Figure 3: Pre and Post Parent Stress Index

Parenting difficulties were assessed with the *Parenting Stress Index* [51]. Only slight improvements in parenting skills were detected.

After the course, dysfunctional episodes have in fact slightly decreased, the families have shown a more involved and conscious reading of the boy's course. In all cases, it was necessary to re-establish clarity with respect to the diagnosis, therefore to work intensely on the information phase to get out of dynamics of denial and overprotection .

Some of the meetings were held “outdoors” by organizing friendly and socializing meetings outside of the care contexts, to strengthen cohesion among the children and test their skills in real life contexts.

It is a widespread experience that, in the clinic of adolescence, previous paths, such as rehabilitation or psychotherapy, seem to run aground, compared to the new psychosocial challenges , and often compared to the objective limits of the boy, as in our case, deficits in EF and borderline IQ.

Managing this type of patient has to do with managing the so-called transition. By transition we mean both the passage of psychic processes from adolescence to adulthood, but also the passage of clinical skills from services for developmental age to those for adults. The transition typically occurs in a delicate period in which young people can experience great changes at different levels: physiological, psychological and social. The evolutionary trajectory of many neurodevelopmental disorders is greatly affected by a weakness in the care offerings precisely in the period of greatest fragility, as now established by a large part of the literature on the subject [52; 53]. Using the GAF Global Functioning scale, it has been seen for example that the transition with "accompaniment" allows a better outcome than that without support in the network of services.

In a 2022 work by Maurice [53] (children diagnosed with ADHD or autism spectrum disorder), it is reaffirmed that an optimal transition should ensure continuity of care or facilitate access to adult services. Any obstacle in the transition process that leads to discontinuity of care can worsen the symptoms of disorders, and ultimately can negatively affect the overall mental health of young people. There are still cultural or operational barriers in the transition process from child services to mental health services and specific recommendations need to be structured to strengthen the interface between the 2 types of services.

This experience, limited in terms of the number of patients, may open the way to the need for further investigation of the topic and to the opportunity for further studies.

Conclusions

In adolescent patients with ED, non-pharmacological interventions are focused on *social skills* and parenting skills.

Group interventions on *Social Skills* and *parent training* do not always produce easily measurable results, and this is reported in the literature as a critical element, however, especially interventions on parenting can produce positive effects even after years.

In this sense, our experience is limited to a small group of problematic adolescents, but it is based on a vast literature and on an evident need for health, and we have represented for the 6 families involved a significant point of reference in a crucial period of the children's lives.

Furthermore, interventions on *Social Skills* in groups represent a resource for public services, both to optimize resources and to work on the most limiting deficits of psychiatric pathologies in adolescence, which are those of a social nature and with wider repercussions on the quality of life of children and families.

Furthermore, given the age group, this experience represents an area of intervention that prepares the processes related to the transition and the inevitable evolutionary steps with respect to global adaptation.

Statement of Informed Consent

Informed consent was obtained from all subjects involved in the study.

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